

Effect of treating single superphosphate with cowdung

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We studied the effect of cowdung-treated single superphosphate (SSP) on panicles/m² and grain yield of rice variety Sita (135 d duration) in a 3-yr wet season field trial. Soil was dark gray, neutral heavy clay (pH 7.1) with poor drainage, medium fertility (0.75% organic C, 0.07% total N, 22 kg available P/ha, 185 kg available K/ha), and CEC 32.1 meq/ 100 g. P fertilizer was mixed with fresh cowdung in a 1:3 ratio 10-12 h before application. Six levels of P in addition to the P content of cowdung were used in a randomized block design with five replications.

Yields from treated plots were significantly higher than from control plots, indicative of nutrient deficiency in the soil (see table). P as SSP mixed with cowdung as a basal dose yielded significantly higher. P increased yields even when applied as late as at maximum tillering.

Both SSP alone and with cowdung applied basally and at maximum tillering increased panicles/m², except for SSP alone at tillering. □

Effect of cowdung-treated single superphosphate (SSP) on yield of grain and panicles of rice.^a Bihar, India, 1983-85.

Treatment ^b	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Mean panicles/m ²
Control (no P)	2.94 c	252 b
17.2 kg P as SSP, basal	3.43 b	270 a
17.2 kg P as SSP, 20 DT	3.35 b	249 b
17.2 kg P as SSP + cowdung (1:3), basal	3.93 a	277 a
17.2 kg P as SSP + cowdung (1:3), 20 DT	3.60 ab	274 a

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.
^bDT = days after transplanting.

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Sources and methods of N application for irrigated wetland rice

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We studied sources and methods of N application for irrigated wetland rice on a sandy loam soil with pH 7.0, organic matter 0.9%, total N 0.07%, and CEC 12.2 meq/ 100 g. The test variety was GR-11.

Prilled urea (PU) local best split and standard best split, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and Massoorie-phosphorus-coated urea (MPCU) at 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ ha were compared. (MPCU is an indigenous material supplied by Madras Fertilizer Limited.)

In the local best split application, PU (46% N) was applied in 4 equal

splits: basal, at maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and booting stage. In standard best split application, PU was applied 2/3 basal and 1/3 topdressed 5 to 7 d before panicle initiation, incorporated with no standing water. SCU (36% N) was incorporated 6 d after transplanting (DT). USG (46% N) was placed in the center of every 4 hills at 10-12 cm soil depth 6 DT. MPCU (32% N) was basally applied and incorporated before transplanting.

Treatment significantly affected panicles/m² (see table). At 87 kg N/ha, USG gave significantly more panicles than SCU.

USG at 58 kg N/ ha yielded significantly higher than MPCU and urea best split. SCU at 87 and 116 kg N/ ha produced significantly higher yields than all treatments except USG. □

Grain yield and panicles/m² with different N sources and application methods, Nawagam, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Form and application method	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)
0	No N	2.16	163
58	PU best split (local)	3.31	203
58	PU standard best split	2.68	210
58	SCU broadcast and incorporated	3.69	280
58	USG placed 10-12 cm deep	4.34	308
58	MPCU broadcast and incorporated	2.91	236
87	PU best split (local)	3.56	249
87	PU standard best split	3.34	247
87	SCU broadcast and incorporated	4.88	289
87	USG placed 10-12 cm deep	4.44	341
87	MPCU broadcast and incorporated	3.70	294
116	PU best split (local)	3.95	277
116	PU standard best split	3.31	273
116	SCU broadcast and incorporated	4.96	296
116	USG placed 10-12 cm deep	4.52	303
116	MPCU broadcast and incorporated	3.90	280
CD (0.05)		0.76	41

Performance of Azospirillum biofertilizer in irrigated and rainfed upland rice

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We studied the field performance of a local isolate of *Azospirillum lipoferum*

under irrigated and rainfed upland conditions.

The irrigated experiment was laid out with IR50 rice in a red sandy loam soil (pH 7.6, EC 0.35 mmho, 265 kg N, 12.2 kg P, 276 kg K/ha). Different levels of fertilizer N with and without *Azospirillum* biofertilizer were compared.

Sixty kg seed/ ha were uniformly coated with 1 kg *Azospirillum*